

Iconography of Somaskanda Panel at Needur Temple

A Study

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ABSTRACT

Sri Somanathaswamy temple at Needur is one of the most ancient temples of Tamil Nadu. Needur is situated four kilometers north of Mayiladuthurai on Mayiladuthurai to Manalmedu route. This temple is now under the control of Hindu Religious and Charitable Endowment Board. Somaskanda and Umamaheswara are two iconographical forms which first appear in the cave and structural temples of early medieval South India in certain isolated packets. One of the most important representations in Pallava times is the Somaskanda panel in the back wall of the sanctum of Siva temples. In the Chola period, the representation of Somaskanda has taken a different form. This group is composed of Siva and Uma with the child Skanda standing between them in one and the same pedestal. The right hand is in Kataka pose and the left is in varadha pose. The earliest inscription of Kulothunga gives information about the construction of the temple and vimana in stone by Kandan Madhavan, the Chief of Milalai Nadu.

Key Words: Location of the place Needur temple, literary evidence of Devaram hymns, Epigraphical records of this temple, Sculptural excellence of Somaskanda panel and its date.

Introduction

Somanathaswamy temple at Needur is one of the most ancient temples of Tamil Nadu. Needur, is a northern suburb of Mayiladuthurai taluk of Mayiladuthurai district. It has a unique place in the history of Saivism. Needur is situated four kilometers north of Mayiladuthurai on Mayiladuthurai to Manalmedu route. Needur has a railway station which is about one kilometer away from this temple. Needur Somanathaswamy is 21st of the 276 Devara Padal Petra Shiva Sthalam. This temple is situated on the northern bank of river Cauvery in Cholanadu (Vadakari). This temple is now under the control of Hindu Religious and Charitable Endowment Board (HR & CE).

Summery

According to this temple legendary history, Needur, Somanatheswarar Swamy along with Toli Amman was worshiped by Surya, Chandra, Kali and Crab. The sacred tree of this temple is the Makilam tree (Botanical Name: Mimusops Elengi). Hence, this place was called as Vakularanyam, Makilaranyam, Magilavanam. Tamil Saiva Saints Tirunavukkarasar (Appar)¹ of 7th century C.E and Sundarar² of 7th century C.E .has sung in praise of the Lord as Needur-Kuttan (the dancer of Needur)

The sacred hymns pertaining to this temple are the first literary evidences proves the existence of the temple in 7th century and the temple was rebuilt in stone in the first decade of the 12th century C.E.(Kulothunag Chola I³ 1070 C.E – 1125C.E) This first inscription data issued in his 18th regnal year of Kulothunag I (1088 C.E) mentions the reconstruction of this temple and Vimana in stone by Kandan Madavan⁴, who was the Vel (chief) of Milalai Nadu. The name of God also mentioned as “Umaiyodu Nilavina Perumal”(Umasahitha). .Further the record also gives information about the political division of the place as Needur, a village in Tiruvindalur Nadu in Sonadu. The place names Needur, Tiruvindalur mentioned in the epigraphs of the early 11th century C.E are still called in the same name. A long gap of (1088 C.E.- 1118 C.E) nearing 30 years of Kulothunga I’s record found on the southern entrance of central shrine issued in his 48th regnal year (1118C.E)⁵ mentions the same information about the construction of the temple

(1088 C.E) . This same matter also engraved on the north eastern entrance of the Chidambaram Nataraja temple⁶.

A damaged record of Rajadhiraja II.(1166 C.E -1182 C.E) found on the eastern side of the outer most wall and the left entrance of the temple issued in his 14th regnal year (1180C.E)..This inscription start with an introduction as Kadal Soozhndha”⁷, who pleased to take Madurai and Ilam (Ceylon)⁸.The political division mentioned in this as, Needur as Rajasikamani Chathurdimangalam, a bramadheyam in Tirvindalur nadu⁹,

The next inscription of this temple, also throws light on the political and societal condition the Chola kingdom under Rajaraja III. An inscriptional data found on the southern wall of the verandha of the prakara of this temple issued in his 16th regnal year (1232 C.E)¹⁰ states, a great assembly met in the Pugalabharana Vinayaga temple in Rajasikamani-Chathurvedi mangalam, a village in the Tiruvindalur Nadu, a sub division of Rajadhiraja Valanadu. The assembly discussed certain revised rules regarding the tenant cultivation. Rajaraja III issued new orders in Chola kingdom after he regained¹¹ his power from Kopperunjinga with the help of Hoysala Vira Narasimha.¹² The inscription record from Needur temple, gives information about the political eclipse prevailed in the days of Rajaraja III (1230 C.E-1232 C.E). After regaining the Chola power (1232 C.E) he revised the rules of tenant cultivation, the clear mentioning of the date of this temple record gives information about the political and social history of the Later Cholas.

The inscriptional data of this temple (1088 C.E) especially during the period of Kulothunga Chola I throws light on the construction of stone temple for “Umaiyoudu Nilavina Perumal”(Umasahitha) by Kandan Madhavan the Vel of Milalai Nadu. This indirectly mentions the bronze idol of Somaskanda panel belong to the last quarter of the 11th century.¹³

Somaskanda and Umamaheswara are two iconographical forms which first appear in the cave and structural temples of early medieval South India in certain isolated packets. One of the most important representations in Pallava times is the Somaskanda panel in the back wall of the sanctum of Siva temples. In the Chola period, the representation of Somaskanda has taken a different form. Somaskanda is the most common sportive form of Siva which received special

worship in almost all the Siva temples of Tamilnadu as one of the Panchamurthis. This group is composed of Siva and Uma with the child Skanda standing between them in one and the same pedestal.

Lord Siva of Needur Somaskanda group (ht.50cm) is seated comfortably on the padmasana in the erect Suhasana pose, i.e., the right leg hangs and the leg is bent cross wise so as to rest flat on the pedestal. He has a fine Jatamakuta is worked beautifully with distinct emblems like dhaurthura flowers, crescent moon and a serpent; but the minor details are not bold relief. The face is square with subtle smile. The left ear holds patra kundala and makara kundala is in the right ear. The ornaments around the neck ware is quiet beautiful and the lower most is prominent. The shoulders are well proportionate and well modeled. This is one of the fine techniques of the Chola artisans, in joining the shoulders which gives a majestic look to the idol.

The contours of the chest of Siva broaden from the waist, a special feature of the Chola sculptures. Around the neck, a simple Kandigai, is carved. Yajnopavita lies in wave form. The Udara-banda is thick and gem set in front. The torso is executed in a classical manner. The fingers of Lord Shiva are worked in Early Chola manner. The Keyuras and Valayas are seen on the arms. In the upper right and left hands he holds an axe and deer. The lower hands are in abhaya and varadha poses respectively on the right and left hands. On the waist, the lion cloth is seen in simple style. The legs are exquisitely worked and the hanging leg is noteworthy. It is interesting that no anklets are seen.

The figure of Uma is equally beautiful with workmanship. She is well executed in Uttakudikasana pose. The Karanda makuta are prominent and graceful. The strands of hairs falling on either side of the shoulders and it reach almost the bands of the Keyuras. Her ears are empty. The elbow ornaments are projected. The necklaces around the neck are set in the ring like one enclosing the rest. Simple tassel is seen hanging from the right shoulder. The torso is proportionate but its modelling throws light on the last phase of the Cholas of Thanjavur¹⁴. Katchu banda are absent. The workmanship of the breasts is to be noted. The postures of the legs are beautifully exposed. The treatment of the garment adds the beauty of image. The right hand is shown in simhakarna pose and the left is in varahasta. Here, Silpa sastras gives description about Uma in the Somaskanda panel has to hold a lily flower on her right.

Suhasana Somaskanda panel, Siva, Uma and Skanda are depicted according to the Silpa Lakshana noted in the Silpa Ratna¹⁵. except the absence of lily flowers. Saraswathi Chitra Karma Sastram¹⁶ gives a detailed description about the Somaskanda panel, here also Uma has to hold Neelothpalam (Lily) flower. Sri Kasyapa Silpa Sastram¹⁷ also gives a detailed account about the absence of flower in Uma's right hand. According to Sakalathikaram¹⁸, Uma has to sit just back side of the Lord Siva, but in Somaskanda panel of Needur temple Lord Siva and Uma are sitting in equal but in separate Padma Peeda. Here, also Uma has to hold flower, but the flower is absent.

Regarding the figure of little Skanda is also interesting. Skanda is shown in front of Uma and Shiva. In the Somaskanda panel, the ornaments such as the Karandamakuta, ear rings, necklaces, Channavira, the waist bands with the tassels hanging from them on either thigh are neatly presented in the image. The right hand is in Kataka pose and the left is in varadha pose.

Conclusion

1. The Saivite hymns of Devaram are the first literary reference of the place Needur and the temple in the 7th century C.E.
2. The legendary history of the temple throws light on the name of Lord Shiva as Somanathar. and it enriches the religious belief of the temple in and around Needur.
3. The earliest inscription of Kulothunga I (1088C.E) gives information about the construction of the temple and vimana in stone by Kandan Madhavan, the chief of Milalai Nadu. Further it mentions the name of the God and Goddess as "Umaiyodu Nilavina Perumal"(Umasahitha)
4. The temple and the place was a village in Tiruvindalur nadu , a subdivision of Rajadhiraja Valanadu and later, from the time of Rajadhiraja II , Needur was in Rajasikamani-Chathurvedi mangalam, a village in the Tiruvindalur Nadu, a sub division of Rajadhiraja Valanadu. The literature, inscriptions mentioned this place as Needur is still continued.
5. The Inscription of Rajaraja III in this temple throws the political and societal conditions of the Chola country.

6. “Umaiyodu Nilavina Perumal” (Umasahitha), Somaskanda panel in Needur is shown in Padmasana over a Bhadrasana with fine proportions and simple moldings.
7. The treatment of this image, especially the face and neckalces are clearly marking it as a Chola bronze.
8. This Somaskanda panel has middle and later Chola characteristics.(transition from middle to late Chola period)
9. Undoubtedly the Somaskanda group of Needur is noteworthy and stylistically assigned to the last quarter of the 11th century C.E.

END NOTES

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